

“MODULAR DESIGN” PRINCIPLES: A DESIGNING APPROACH FOR A PROPOSED STYLE OF MULTI-INSPIRATION ABAYA

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Abstract

Climate change have been caused by industrial revolution, one part of this revolution is the appearance of what is called fast fashion, which involve the concept of short time consumption, therefore short time profit, thus the urgent need to protect the environment, and the consumers' awareness have been increased and became a necessity. several approaches have been experimented in fashion, design, and production to achieve the principles of sustainability, one of these approaches is Modularity, this approach specifically based on idea of (dividing), that means divide the aggregate product into smaller units, called (modules). In current study, the design researcher experiments a proposed modular Abaya trend which evokes many inspirations in only one basic composition through attach/detach modules, the researcher named this style of product a "multi-inspiration fashion", which achieving various aesthetic appearances with more than one inspiration. The research followed the experimental development methodology through identifying modular design system and analysing some of remarkable modular fashion experiments and designs. Four Multi-inspirations Abaya were designed inspired by the six modular methods.

Keywords: Abaya- Modular Design- Sustainable Fashion- Multi-inspiration Fashion- Transformative Fashion.

INTRODUCTION

Modularity in fashion means the consisting quality of separate parts that, when combined, form a complete whole, composing a garment involves consisting of many parts together through sewing, therefore the principle of modularity can be applied on fashion as it's in architecture and interior design and other industry areas. Because the applications of sustainability in fashion production have many methods, such as the use of natural materials, natural dyes, recycling, and upcycling, etc., one of these methods is the sustainable design' structure, the idea, and the techniques. The modularity approach represents an application of sustainability, as it allows the design of garment to be changed several times, which saves the consumer from falling under the influence of fast fashion.

Current study focuses on identifying the applications of modularity in fashion and proposing a trend of multi modular women' Abaya which change its aesthetics depending on the attach/detach modules. some experiments would be produced for utilizing the modularity approach, and this is the second phase of the research, the main objective that garment modules achieve multi aesthetic appearance, based on the the component parts.

The modular system in fashion design achieves the production of more than one design appearance in a single composition whose parts change, achieving an economical consumption and reduces spending by the individual and society. Reduces environmental exposure to pollutants and raises the awareness of community members about environmental causes, thus achieving the three principles of sustainability: economy, society, and environment.

Problem Statement

The problem of the study represented in adopting the modular approach in designing women's Abaya, so that the multiplicity of the aesthetic appearance of a single abaya is achieved through attach/detach modules.

Accordingly, the study attempts to answer the sub-research questions, as following:

- 1- What is modular fashion? What are its categories?
- 2- What are the most distinguished experiments carried out by researchers and designers in modular fashion?
- 3-What is the possibility of designing a collection of women's Abaya that suits Muslim women, following a modular approach to achieve multiplicity aesthetic appearance?

Objectives

- 1- Identify the categories of modular fashion.
- 2- Identify the experiments of researchers and designers and the most achieved results.
- 3- Proposing a fashion collection for women's Abayas applying the modularity approach that achieving aesthetic multiplicity.

Significance

- The current study is an experimental and applied study in the field of fashion design and production, which is one of the areas of entrepreneurship, small and medium enterprises. Modularity represents one of sustainable design' applications.
- The applied designs are an innovative experiment in the field of apparel manufacturing as well.
- Multi-modules applications in the field of design and production are one of the sustainability approaches in the fashion industry.
- The proposed applications can be produced and presented to the market in the Arab Gulf countries.
- The proposed designs represent a preliminary phase to produce the "multi-inspiration Abaya" for obtaining intellectual property.
- The study represents an addition to specialized libraries and designers, that applications of fashion for Arab and Muslim women in general still require many experiments and applications.

Methodology

-Experimental Development Method: Systematic work on existing knowledge gained from research and/or practical experiences which is directed to producing new materials, products and installing new process, systems, or improving substantially those already produced. The current study is working on experimenting new system of designing and producing women Abaya following the modularity approach to achieve multiplicity aesthetic appearance.

1- MODULAR DESIGN AND MODULA FASHION DEFINITIONS

Modularity Definition: "Modularity can be defined as the degree to which the components of the system can be separated and recombined to create variety of configuration without losing its functionality" (Ovtchinnikova, 2011 from Schilling, 2000). Modular design refers to a construction design by organizing sub-assemblies and components as interconnected building modules, that can be integrated through specific methods to construct the complete composition. (Tseng, M.M., & others 2018)

In 1965, In 1965, the concept of modular design was first presented by Martin stark where it was proposed to

use modular product in manufacturing as a new approach of multiplicity, which enable modifying specific modules for accessing new requirements without influencing the main structure, it has been utilized in many productions. (Qurashi, W.A.E. ,2022 from Tseng, M. M., & others, 2018)

Brands and fashion designers began in the 1960s and 1970s experiment with the concept of detachable elements, from skirts that could be transformed into trousers to jackets with removable sleeves. The 1990s and early 2000s saw the rapidly growing concept of Fast Fashion, which, while affordable and varied, aroused fears about environmental impact and sustainability. (*What is Modular Clothing?* 2023) Today, with the growing move towards sustainable practices and the increasing value to multiplicity, durable products, modular fashion is at the forefront of production innovation and continues to evolve more experiments and applications.

The clothing's modular system dismantles the clothes parts separately, and each part as a module can be disassembled to reconstruct with others. Modular system makes the clothing no longer as a complete product, but as a whole composition of multiple modules. The modules can be integrated as the wearer prefers and achieve multi-appearance possibilities. (Li, M. M., & others 2018)

2- THE VALUE OF MODULAR APPROACH IN FASHION DESIGN

The value of modular approach in fashion designing is represented in three main features.

1) Diversity: Modular design greatly enhances the interactivity in between the design and the wearer, it maximizes the care of the wearer's emotions and needs, that the wearer participates in the design configurations and the design's appearance, on the other hand, modular design can change the clothing aesthetic appearance through different module assembly, also it can meet different styles and different needs, it collects many dresses in one dress, this reduces consumption cost, anti-environmental practices and enhance sustainability practices.

2) flexibility: The conventional system of manufacturing fashion must undergo five processes including design, production, sales, use and discard the use. Compared to the modular design approach of designing and producing clothes which has a high degree of flexibility in each process, the seller can design the modules according to market demand, the wearer can also adapt the design based on oneself requirements. Modularity enables us to achieve efficient resources and low energy consumption, that's what the low-carbon environment needs. (Li, M. M., & others 2018)

3) Creativity: The many possibilities to create variations in the design and how it looks like at the end in each time, with endless creative applications for both the designer and the wearer, modularity not only put the wearer as a part of designing process but also enhancing the creativity thinking of the wearer and constructing an intimate communication in between the clothing and the wearer-self.

3- THE VALUE OF MODULAR APPROACH IN FASHION PRODUCTION

-In the aspect of Quality modular design of clothing ensures the design quality as much as possible while making the garment series products efficiently, success of the whole design depends on the accuracy of each part or module.

- In the aspect of Market, it achieves flexible design space for the designers, and enhances the market embracing of clothing design products based on effective production.

- In the aspect of garment market Research, it's a wide space on the detailed analysis to each module, the design, and the function, thus forming a garment management system with certain standardization.

- In the aspect of clothing After-sale treatment, it can also be targeted for the garment production responsibility division, in which way can achieve the purpose of accurately and efficiently finding up/solving problems. (Zhou, F., & others 2020)

4- MODULARIZING THE PRODUCT: (MODULAR METHODS)

For understanding the modularity, first it's necessary to define the term module. A module is a component or some components that can attach/detach as a unit, the module provides an additive function to the product. (Nadasbas, & Cileroglu, 2017 from Allen & Carlson, 1998)

There are four characteristics of the modules: Modules are cooperative, they have functional interactions, they have one or more specific function which could be isolated from the whole system, finally modules are

independent, this can be re-configure to result a different overall outcome. (Nadasbas, & Cileroglu, 2017 from Marshall, & others 1998)

A study by Ulrich and Tung (1991) identified six methods of product modularity which can be used separately or in combination for producing a product. Their typology indicates that modularity is multifaceted concept, and it illustrates that the final product can be constructed and reconstructed through various configurations. Figure n. (1) presents these six methods of product modularity; each method of them will be explained in brief.

1-Component sharing modularity: The same component can be used in more than one product.

2-Component swapping modularity: Components are assembled for completing the product.

3-Cut-to-fit modularity: This method allows for minimal processing before using the product.

4-Bus modularity: This method involves a base and modular component which are installed to the base in combination.

5-Sectional modularity: This method allows the product to achieve different purposes.

6-Mix modularity: Which allows for a mixture of different modules.

Fig. (1) Modularity methods in product design. (Ovtchinnikova, A. 2011 from Ulrich & Tung, 1991)

From: <https://aaltodoc.aalto.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/aac85312-64d9-4272-a909-984704f5f9df/content>

5- MODULAR DESIGN CATEGORIES IN FASHION

Li, Chen, and Wang (2018) Proposed three classifications of modular fashion, according to different disassembly type.

- The component modular fashion: the basic clothing form is retained.
- The geometric modular fashion: separated from the basic clothing.
- The compounded modular fashion is adopted both.

1-Component modular fashion: component modular design, retains the basic structure of clothing, clothing will be disassembled into many modules, which can departure from the original clothing structure, break up the whole into parts, each part of the module is part of the clothing, to ensure the module in combination, can restore the original shape of clothing. Here, according to functional attributes of modules, the component modules are refined into two categories: single function module and multi-function module.

A-Single function module means that a disassembled module only has a fixed function, and a module has

only one form of splicing. The decomposition of a single functional module only needs to be taken apart from the complete garment, it's the most used currently.

B-Multi function module means that the module has two or more functions, multi-function can be achieved, in addition to simple disassembly like single function module, but also through the conversion.

2-Geometric modular fashion: geometric modular design usually dismantling the clothing out of the basic form, it dismantled into geometric shapes such as triangle, or polygon, even the geometric size of the module can be small or large, clothing can be structured by one or various types of geometric modules, the splicing way can be flat, and can be three-dimensional. This allow for more flexibility than the component modular design, many replication modules can be used, the modules can replace each other like Lego blocks.

3- The compounded modular fashion is adopted both the component, and the geometric modular fashion.

Modular Fashion Splicing: The substantial principle involved in modularity of the common splicing techniques including buttons, snap fasteners and zippers, knots have strong decorative effect. The thermal activation adhesive film is convenient, but the cost is high, and the modules could not be disassembled again.

6- MODULAR FASHION' DESIGNERS AND RESEARCHERS EXPERIMENTS

One of the earliest designers worked with the concept of modularity is the Spanish fashion designer Paco Rabanne, in his couture collection 1966 the designer made no-sew dresses made of linked plastic and metal, he liberated fashion from the needle and fabric. (Person, 2020) for Spring 2021, the designers of his brand followed suit, creating looks in his image. (Fig. 2-3)

Fig. (2)

Fig. (3)

Fig. (2) Paco Rabanne couture collection 1960s used geometric modular shapes with linking techniques. Fig. (3) The designer collection for Spring 2021, same concept, and applied technique.

From: <https://www.vogue.com/article/paco-rabanne-link-dresses-inspire-designers-for-spring-2021>

Dutch Designer Berber Soepboer, with Fioen van Balgooi experimented a project entitled "Fragment Textiles", in their project the design completely changes in color and in form appearance. The project is based on two designs, one employing square- pieces and the other integrating star-shaped of the same material. The design is changeable in color and style, the modules can be reconstructed in new appearance to create a variety of colors and forms without sewing. (*From Uniform Polyhedral to Fashion, 2011*) the objective of the project is to examine the technique of click/fold in producing fashion through multiple modules which can be changed and recycled easily, the customer will have less need for buying new clothes to obtain different designs. (Balgooi, 2009) (Fig. 4-6)

Fig (4)

Fig. (5)

Fig (6)

Fig. (4-6) Click/fold technique by designers Berber Soepboer and Fioen van Balgooi in the project entitled "Fragment Textile."

From: <https://www.refinity.eu/fragment-textiles.html>

Japanese designer Kosuke Tsumura in his project "Cocoon cradle" created clothing for a mother and her baby made from felibendy™, a material that is so soft like a silk, cocoon mother clothing is modular like puzzle pieces. (Hustic, 2010) The composition of the clothing fabric construction depends mainly on the interlocking of the module parts together through the protruding and recessed parts in the shape of a circle. (Fig. 7-10)

Fig. (7)

Fig. (8)

Fig. (9)

Fig. (10)

Fig (7-10): The project "Cocoon Cardel" by designer Kosuke Tsumura

From: <https://www.designboom.com/design/kosuke-tsumura-cocoon-cradle-and-mother-piece-for-tokyo-fiber-09-senseware/>

From: <https://www.body-pixel.com/2010/04/04/kosuke-tsumuras-subtle-senses-gallery/>

Mia Cullin the Finish furniture and textile designer, almost her all designs consist of flat fabric which is constructed by interlocking between two shapes, the shape of protruding outward and vacuum parts inside. (Fig. 11-13) A project by designer Susan Myers (2016) "No sew Project" locking the cut pieces together by pulling the arrow-shaped tabs through the slots. Aurelie Tu founder of Crafted systems, the forum for experimentation. The first created products were from felt, involved a simple system of slots and tongues whereby the felt locks into itself without need for stitching or any fasteners, The process is simply an interactive of creating new geometry and patterns.

Fig. (11)

Fig. (12)

Fig. (13)

Fig. (11-13) Fabric constructions through replicating the modules by designer Mai Cullin

From: <https://www.miacullin.com/>

Researcher Eunsuk Hur, her project aimed to encourage the public to stop being passive consumers and to become a part of the design process, also to give consumers ownership over their fashion products. To the objectives, the project proposed transformative modular sustainable fashion. The findings indicated that consumers found it easy to design their own clothing and that they experienced increased interest in the design production process changing ordinary materials from the ordinary into interactive process' design. (Hur, 2015) (Fig. 14-15). The project by researchers Chanjuan Chen and Kendra Lapolla explored modular shapes and interlocking systems through practice approach. (Fig. 16-17) The modular approach allowed designers to experiment with different shapes and interlocking types, the experiment included four designs. The interactive nature of the modules encouraged creative exploration. (Chen, Lapolla, 2020)

Fig. (14)

Fig. (15)

Fig. (16)

Fig. (17)

Fig. (14) & Fig. (15) modular and transformative designs by researcher Eunsuk Hur.

From: <https://www.eunsukhur.com/publications>

Fig. (16) & Fig. (17) modular fashion and interlocking systems by Chanjuan Chen and Kendra Lapolla.

From: <http://www.chanjuanchen.com/modularity.html>

Martijn Van Strien, Dutch designer in his collection “The post-couture” allowed consumers to download, customize, produce, and self-assemble clothing designs. Each of the modules can be personalized to the buyer's individual need and measurements. The collection was inspired by architecture and have been implemented through laser-cut technique, involving the concept of no need to sewing machine, The designs made from Spacer Fabric – a 3D-knitted material like neoprene and made from recycled PET bottles. (Fig. 18-20) Mansour (2017) classified modular system to two categories; first is the garment panels, thus garment is divided into several parts which are removable and enable to exchange with other parts, second is the Lego-like system, thus the garment is constructed through repeating of one pattern like Lego components in different sizes, in her research experiment, she integrated modularity concept with dart manipulation for

proposing women fashion on the mannequin. Hassaan, (2020) proposed the “Mosaic Motifs Structure” as a strategy for academicians when teaching fashion students the practical courses such as Hand Embroidery the experiment resulted a fashion collection by the students', consisted of many mosaic -modular-embroidered motifs, which formed on mannequin in many compositions.

Fig. (18)

Fig. (19)

Fig. (20)

Fig. (18-20) Martijn Van Strien, the “Post couture” collection.

From: <https://www.dezeen.com/2015/10/18/martijn-van-strien-the-post-couture-collective-customisable-fashion-dutch-design-week-2015/>

Rudneva, Lunina, Belik, Tashpulatov, Cherunova, and Sabiova (2023) offered a new method of modular fashion based on polyhedral unfolds construction, The design can transform from a short jacket into a handbag, through its composition that is based on hexagonal and pentagonal modules. Lenawati, and Rachmawaty (2021) proposed a ready to wear modular fashion design which can be disassembled, the design structure is inspired by the traditional Indonesian houses Woloan Minahasa. Qurashi, (2022) found out through experimental practice through geometric modules have been designed on the mannequin inspired by Islamic motifs, that simple geometric shaped reflect the Islamic art aesthetics and enable the designer to control the interlocking process easily. Rashad, (2023) utilized the modular and reversible fashion in her experiments to produce contemporary sustainable fashion inspired by baroque, the applications indicated how modular fashion enhances conscious consumption and it has a positive effect on reducing waste, the designs integrated between “modularity” and “Transformism” concepts. Samkry, and Tawfik, (2022) utilized the modular approach to propose a transformative dress inspired by snow microscopic crystal, the dress produced from velvet fabric and fabricated within laser cut technique, the modules were not being separated, but elastic, and the characteristic of elasticity allowed for multi forming on the mannequin. Agata Kycia explored the potentials of textile forming through 3D printing on prestressed fabric, the experiment resulted various degrees of shrinkage within the samples, although the experiment objective is for production in the field of building industry, to obtain materials that are easy to form with light weight. (Kycia, n.d) What has been presented can be similarly used in innovative applications in the field of fashion, which mainly rely on the idea of modules that can be formed manually to give a three-dimensional effect on the body. Zaghlool, and Rashidi, (2023) integrated between modularity and transformism in proposing zero waste evening wear for adolescent girls, they considered modular design system is a category of transformative fashion categories, in addition to reversible and folding/tying methods, the results represented in designing and implementing of zero-waste transformative dresses which fulfill both functional and aesthetic needs.

7- ARABIC ABAYA

Women's abayas were not among the pieces included in women's fashion lists as they are today, but they were a traditional outfit consisting of a long dress with sleeves of various designs. Most of the people who wore this piece were Arab women in the desert, the countryside, and the cities in the Levant, Iraq, Egypt, and the Gulf countries. Arab as an inherent part of the faith, customs and traditions in those countries, and this dress was called the burqa, niqab and abaya. Some researchers believe that black women's abayas were found in the wardrobe of Arab women and surrounding civilizations 4,000 years ago. This opinion came

from women's clothing in Mesopotamia, where drawings were found indicating that women in those eras wore fashions with long and wide designs similar in design to the abaya. Researchers have confirmed that whoever was wearing the abaya and hijab at that time indicates that she was living a luxurious life, as it was some clothing for someone who did not work or belonged to a wealthy family. The abaya took a valuable place as a garment for Muslim women. Once the instructions of the Islamic religion spread in the Arab world, abaya has become one of the pieces that express religious principles, with profound implications, and it repels prying eyes. (Salim, n.d)

8- PROPOSED MULTI-INSPIRATION ABAYA

The design researcher applied two methods in each design, the 6th modular method has been applied in 4 designs.

Design [1] + [2]: Figures 21- 22.

Abaya's construction: H shape long abaya, with long sleeves, curved cutlines on the top right front (modular), 4 circular holes on the left side with long scarf which passes through the holes to be filled with the fabric.

Modular design methods: Component sharing and component swapping.

The draped fabric as a scarf considers a main module of the abaya' design, the wearer can control the scarf color' design and draping on the left side, can also replacing between the scarf on the right and the left sides.

Multi- inspiration concept of the design: The multiplicity possibility of choosing the draping style, textures, and surface design of the fabric on the right and left sides allows the wearer a wide scale of shaping the aesthetics and expression of the abaya, may be geometric with neutral colors or floral patterns with vibrant colors.

Splicing techniques: The holes with crossing fabric on the left side, and snap fasteners on the right side.

Design [3] + [4]: Figures 23- 24.

Abaya's construction: Long sleeves, top part with modules, underpart with modules.

Modular design methods: Bus, Mix and swapping modular design.

The sleeves are divided into four sequenced parts, the wearer can replace between the three parts after the armhole part, the underpart can be added by mesh fabric to give a new aesthetic effect in the design, also the upper cut module is changeable.

Multi- inspiration concept of the design: The design can be in geometric style in white and black style or can be in plain fabric with floral cuts in vital colors. The design allows many choices for the wearer.

Splicing techniques: Zippers in the sleeves, and snap fasteners for the underpart.

Fig. (21) Design [1]

Fig. (22) Design [2]

Fig. (23) Design [3]

Fig. (24) Design [4]

Fig. (21-22) proposed modular Abaya.

9- RECOMMENDATIONS

- Designers adopting the modular approach in designing common lifestyle products for its ideal characteristics which match contemporary users' needs.
- The increasing awareness of fashion designers to apply different sustainability methods.
- Organizing seminars by the fashion institutions for increasing community awareness about the benefits of sustainability in general, and sustainability of clothing in particular.
- More studies and experiments on methods of clothing sustainability, and how the modular approach can be recruited in fashion applications which meet the needs of community members.
- Funding the second phase of the study, represented in the actual application of the multi-inspired women's abaya, designed based on the modular approach, advertising it in Arab markets positively.

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